

LOW TEMPERATURE TOUGHNESS COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF THERMOPLASTIC AND THERMOSET MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A toughness comprehensive study of 914 epoxy and PMR-15 thermoset and PEEK thermoplastic matrix composites over the low temperature range (down to -196°C) is presented. The critical fracture energy of unidirectional composites and corresponding matrixes is examined.

The paper describes how cracks propagate through the various matrixes and more extensively, why the toughness is higher in relation to the matrix nature. Results show that if the toughness of matrixes is increased when the plastic deformation zone at the crack tip is more extended, the fibres which divide this plastic zone impair the toughness of thermoplastic composites dramatically.

1. INTRODUCTION

The delamination is a main cause of damage in laminated composites and therefore a major parameter for the design of structure intended for use in an environment of low temperatures. The mode I resistance explains the level of toughness of the orthotropic material although the inhomogeneity and the anisotropy of fibre composites are together responsible for the fact that the crack growth is always complex. For evaluating the mode I toughness, there are numerous theoretical and experimental methods [1] but none of them is simple and the low temperatures add a supplementary difficulty.

In this paper, we determine by means of the Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics the critical fracture energy, G_{IC} , of resins and composites. The paper reports the toughness measurements over the range from -196°C to room temperature of thermoset and thermoplastic resins and corresponding unidirectional composites. A great deal of interest has been expressed for the polyimide resins due to their thermal stability and for thermoplastic matrixes due to their extensive plasticity. Based on the measurements, the paper describes how cracks propagate across the matrix and why there are discrepancies between matrixes and between a composite and its matrix.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1. Materials and processing conditions

i) Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) resin and AS4 carbon fibre / PEEK composite (APC 2) processed with standard moulding conditions recommended by ICI

ii) PMR-15 polyimide resin and T800 carbon fibre/PMR-15 from GEC Alsthom processed

with 315°C/4H and pressure 60 and 14 bars for polymer and laminate respectively.

iii) 914 epoxy resin and T300 carbon fibre/914 epoxy from Ciba-Geigy. 914 resin was processed by casting (180°C/2H) and laminate by press (180°C/2H/7 bars).

The three composite materials were formed from 24 unidirectional prepreg plies each with a pre-crack (Teflon insert of 25 μm thick). [2].

2.2. Specimens and testing methods

i) Two methods have been applied to determine the toughness of polymers. The first method is based on the stress state at the crack tip of a standard Compact Tension Specimen (CTS). Under plane strain conditions, specimens were characterized by the critical stress intensity factor, K_{IC} , from ASTM standard.

The second method is based on the released elastic energy per crack area of a chevron specimen (fig. 1) [3]. This specimen has the advantage of presenting a high stress concentration at the tip of the chevron notch so that a small load is sufficient to initiate the crack propagation without giving rise to catastrophic rupture. Under plane deformation conditions, specimens were characterized using the energy area intergration method [4] :

$$G_{IC} = - \frac{dU}{dA} \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{array}{l} U : \text{release energy} \\ A : \text{created new crack area} \end{array}$$

ii) The toughness of composite materials was determined from mode I delamination of Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimens. The critical fracture energy, G_{IC} , was calculated from the equation [5] :

$$G_{IC} = \frac{P_c^2 c}{2b} \frac{dc}{da} \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{array}{l} P_c : \text{critical load} \\ b : \text{specimen width} \\ a : \text{crack length} \\ c : \text{DCB compliance} \end{array}$$

For determining the derivative dc/da from the experimental compliance, a fitting from $C = f(a)$ was performed by using of a third order polynomial form : $c = \alpha a^3 + \beta a + \gamma$ [2].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A testing machine (Adamel DY 26) was used to carry out tensile tests of resins and composites. The cross-head speed was 0,1 mm.mn⁻¹ except for several particular conditions. Three specimens were tested for each of four temperatures : 20°C, -55°C, -100°C and -196°C. A chamber cooled by circulating of liquid nitrogen was used for -55°C and -100°C. The lowest temperature was obtained by submerging of the specimen in liquid nitrogen inside an insulating container. The observation of specimens was made through a window of the chamber or container. DCB and CT specimens were pre-cracked (~ 0,2 mm and 2 mm respectively) at room temperature [2].

3.1. Resins

Physically, an elastic or elasto-plastic deformation energy must be present in the resin for propagating a crack. This deformation energy is dependent on main structural factors such as polymer nature, molecular mass, orientation (crystallinity) or crosslinking, polydispersity...

The 914 epoxy contains approximately 20 % volume of polyethersulfone (PES). Its mainly three-dimensional structure leads to a negligible plastic deformation volume at the crack tip. Therefore, the critical stress intensity factor, K_{IC} , describes perfectly the elastic stress state of a CT specimen (under ASTM standard) and the linear elasticity relation between the two fracture criteria, K and G , may be applied. For in-plane stresses and for all temperatures (from 20°C down to -196°C), the following relationship is valid : $G_{IC} = K_{IC}^2/E$ (fig.3) where E is the elastic modulus determined at the same temperatures (fig.2) [6].

An admissible maximum stress applied in a PEEK CT specimen leads to an almost generalized plastification in front of the crack tip so that it is impossible to propagate rapidly a crack at 20°C under plane deformation conditions (generally, specimen breaks in several pieces [7]) and therefore to exhibit the elastic stress state of the material by means of the K_{IC} measurement. On the contrary, the fracture energy may be determined on a chevron specimen and by using the experimental method as defined in 2.2.

For this ductile material at room temperature, the plastic deformation energy which is necessary for crack propagation does not allow to relate the determined G criterion (fig 3) to the K criterion. The crystalline structure of the PEEK which is made of linear chains give rise to a strain at break of 26 % and an ultimate tensile stress of 100 MPa. These two characteristics confer to the material a good toughness.

At liquid nitrogen temperature, the extent of macromolecular movements is substantially reduced and the intermolecular cohesion is reinforced. The PEEK breaking strain falls down to 3 % whereas ultimate stress raises up to 170 MPa. This last mechanical property gives an excellent toughness for the material. It may be noted, however that there is a temperature raise around the crack tip. The speed of crack growth and weak thermal diffusivity of the polymer modify slightly the temperature in the center of the chevron specimen [8].

The PMR 15 resin structure is intermediate between that of the PEEK made of linear chains and that of the 914 epoxy made of a network. The PMR-15 resin crosslink density obtained from oligomers ($M_w \sim 1500$) depends on the number of Diels Alders and retro Diels Alders reactions at cure temperature [9]. For a cure of 315°C/4H, breaking strain ($\epsilon_r \sim 3,7\%$) determined at room temperature is high compared with that determined usually on thermoset resins having a high T_g (320°C for PMR-15). It seems that moulding conditions recommended for giving optimum properties in the composite are not sufficient for fully crosslinking of the resin alone. Therefrom, the PMR-15 resin gets partly a plastic nature and therefore the toughness of the PMR-15 determined from CT 10 specimens increases when testing temperature decreases down to liquid nitrogen temperature (fig.3). A physical analysis having regard to the cure and mechanical properties will follow in order to understand more precisely the enhancement of this toughness.

3.2. Composites

The fracture energy measurements were determined at the crack initiation, G_{IC} . The curve

of fracture energy during crack propagation, G_{ICp} , is generally a R curve which is not an intrinsic characteristic of the composite material since it is dependent on the processing conditions [10]. G_{ICI} which represents the toughness of the matrix measured in the composite can be compared to G_{IC} determined on resin alone. However, the inherent toughness of the matrix is generally higher than that of the overall composite. As foresaid, the toughness of a material is defined by its plastic deformation capacity and its yield point. Now, the matrix is plastically constrained between the fibres. Its plastic flow at the crack tip is seriously reduced by the fibres volume fraction without a compensatory increase in modulus and strength. This composite effect impairs dramatically the toughness of ductile matrix composites. The fracture energy values are presented in fig. 4.

T300/914 composite shows a constant G_{ICI} slightly lower than the corresponding resin G_{IC} in the tested temperature range. Resin and composite both have a low toughness as that seen usually in thermoset matrix composites. They are reference materials in this paper.

For AS4/PEEK composite, the fibres inside plastic deformation volume substantially modify the matrix flow. The effective toughness of the matrix and that of the composite decreases by an order of magnitude compared to that of the neat polymer. The same effect is observed at room or liquid nitrogen temperature. However, the plastic deformation capacity of the matrix is much lower at -196°C ($\epsilon_r \sim 3\%$) and in spite of the increase of the yield point of PEEK ($\sigma_y \sim 170\text{ MPa}$), the toughness at the scale of the composite is reduced. At lower temperature (at liquid helium for example), there should be an equivalent toughness of composites whatever the matrix nature (in interrupted lines in fig. 4).

On the other hand, the fibre misalignment which gives rise to a R curve during the cracking also perturbs the crack initiation. This problem which is not observed in thermoset matrix composites appears clearly in this ductile matrix composite. Figure 5 depicts a plastic deformation zone (rough circular form) in front of a pre-cracked tip at initiation. When the fibres are perfectly aligned (fig 5a), the crack tip grows through the matrix with the crack path guided by the fibres. On the contrary, when the fibres are misaligned (fig. 5b), the crack path runs against fibres so that the plastic volume is divided. The macroscopic plastic deformation is reduced and the crack path is modified leading to lower G_{ICI} and a R curve respectively. Figure 6 summarizes the situation of the thermoplastic composite from initiation to crack propagation.

- curve 1 : perfectly aligned fibres give a constant G_{IC}
- curve 3 : substantially misaligned fibres give a lower G_{ICI} then a very exalted R curve.
- curve 2 : slightly misaligned fibres give an intermediate G_{ICI} followed of a R curve less pronounced.

The toughness of the T800/PMR-15 composite is slightly higher than that of the epoxy-based composite. Contrary to the PEEK matrix, PMR-15 polyimide has a breaking strain which varies very little with the temperature. The disturbance of the small plastic deformation zone does not promote the effect observed in the AS4/PEEK composite at room temperature. Results between room and liquid nitrogen temperatures are not significantly different. It may be noted, however, that the T800/PMR-15 composite presents the best toughness of thermoset matrix composites used to day. Owing to the thermostability of properties de PMR-15 resin, cryogenic applications may be foreseen.

4. CONCLUSION

Toughness of thermoplastic and thermoset matrix composites has been measured at room and towards low temperatures. The main conclusions are :

i) the high plastic deformation of the PEEK does not allow to determine its critical stress intensity factor at room temperature. The fracture energy is only measurable using, for example, a chevron specimen. Toughness is very high owing to both yield point and plastic deformation capacity. This last characteristic falls off dramatically at liquid nitrogen temperature but yield point which is substantially increased raises still higher its toughness. Concerning the AS4/PEEK composite, the fibres volume content perturbs the plastic deformation volume of the matrix at the crack tip and consequently the toughness is very seriously impaired.

ii) The PMR-15 polyimide and 914 epoxy thermoset resins have a weak plastic deformation capacity and approximately the same fracture strength that PEEK at room temperature. K_{IC} or G_{IC} results very well represent the intensity of elastic stresses at the rupture of resins. The crosslinking of the epoxy resin keeps both breaking strain and stress at low temperatures so that the toughness is practically unchanged. Moreover, low toughness of the resin results in a low toughness of the corresponding composite.

PMR-15 shows an enhanced toughness between room and liquid nitrogen temperatures owing to its pseudoplastic nature. Concerning the T800/PMR-15 composite, the plastic deformation capacity of the matrix is perturbed by the fibres but much less than with the PEEK matrix what however gives a toughness slightly higher than for the 914 epoxy based composite.

Finally, matrix nature and fibre volume are the two main parameters governing toughness of the composite. The fibres considerably reduce the plastic character of the matrix without improving so much its strength in the whole composite. In fact, toughness is obtained as if the composite ignored for a large part the plastic contribution of the matrix. This composite effect leads to a convergence of toughness results when thermoplastic and thermoset composites are tested towards low temperatures.

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Figure 1 : Geometrical form of a chevron specimen

Figure 2 : Young's modulus versus temperature of three resins.

Figure 3 : Critical fracture energy as a function of testing temperature.

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Figure 4 : Critical fracture energy at crack initiation as a function of testing temperature

Figure 5 : Alignment of fibres inside PEEK plastic deformation zone at crack initiation and at room temperature, a) aligned fibres, b) misaligned fibres.

Figure 6 : G_{1c} curves as a function of the crack propagation of AS4/PEEK composites at room temperature, ① aligned fibres, ② and ③ misaligned fibres (R curves).